

Matrix product forms for the characteristic polynomial coefficients of poly(*p*-phenylene) graphs

Piyali Ghosh, Somnath Karmakar and Bholanath Mandal*

Department of Chemistry, The University of Burdwan, Burdwan-713 104, West Bengal, India

E-mail : piyali1979@gmail.com, skarmakarbu@rediffmail.com, bmandal_05@yahoo.com

Fax : 91-342-2567938

Manuscript received online 16 August 2013, accepted 04 July 2014

Abstract : The expressions for the characteristic polynomial (CP) coefficients both in matrix product and analytical forms for linear poly(*p*-phenylenes) (PPP) with different end groups (R_s , $s = 1, 2$) such as hydrogen, methylene, allyl, pentadienyl and of their various combinations have been presented that require only the CP coefficients of the starting units, say, of $R_1-C_6H_4-R_2$. The expression so obtained has been found to be independent on the end group(s) considered and is used to obtain the expression for the sum of the CP coefficients, Z'_{N_r} , analogous to the Hosoya index, for any such PPP. Both the expressions of CP and the respective sums of their coefficients for such PPPs have been shown to be reduced in the forms of transfer matrices.

Keywords : Poly(*p*-phenylenes), symmetry plane fragments, characteristic polynomial (CP), sum of CP coefficients, transfer matrix.

Introduction

Characteristic polynomial (CP), a graph invariant, can be obtained by expanding the secular determinant, $|x\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A}|$, of a graph¹⁻⁴ and is written in the form,

$$P(G; x) = |x\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A}| = \sum_j^N a_j x^{N-j} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{A}$ and $\mathbf{I}$ are the adjacency and unit matrices respectively of the same dimension. Due to inherent combinatorial complexity for large polymeric graphs like linear poly(*p*-phenylenes) (PPP), it is a formidable problem to express CP of the polymer in terms of its monomer or starting unit. Before going to detailed discussion let us review some existing methods for obtaining the CPs of graphs. A method based on Sachs theorem⁵ is one of them, where the CP coefficients have been shown to be expressed as sum over of various subgraphs. This method has extensively been used by Graovac *et al.*⁶. Sachs theorem can be generalized for polymeric chains having simple and small repeating units but this become too much cumbersome for large and complicated molecules. Symmetry properties have been used by several authors⁷⁻⁹ for ob-

taining CP coefficients of various chemical graphs. Graph having some sorts of symmetry, the CP appears in factored forms¹⁰⁻¹². Randić¹³ showed the use of Young diagrams and traces of adjacency matrices of graphs for the determination of their CP coefficients. El-Basil^{14,15} used Lucas sequence and Fibonacci relations to generate the CP coefficients for very large graphs. Very recently the algorithms for calculation of the CP coefficients for alternant edge weighted graphs of linear chains have been developed and subsequently been used to evaluate the same for linear poly(*p*-phenylene) graphs¹⁶. Many of these interesting chemical compounds have novel photophysical properties¹⁷⁻²². A significant surge of research activity^{16,23} targeting such materials is still going on. Besides the photophysical properties such molecules have been found to be used in the study of molecular electronic devices (MED)²⁴⁻²⁷. Recently transmission function of poly(*p*-phenylenes) in terms of its sub-units within tight-binding approximation has been analyzed by Fowler *et al.*^{26,27} with the use of the roots of opacity polynomials. Opacity polynomial is a polynomial resulting from the combination of characteristic polynomials of the composite graphs

whose root gives the necessary condition for vanishing of transmission (opacity) in source sink potential model²⁷. Very recently a good linear correlations of such properties of PPP with the $W^{1/4}$ (W is the Wiener index)²⁸ and sum of CP coefficients (Z'_{N_r}) have been established¹⁶. In the present study algorithms with the use of plane of symmetry for calculating CP coefficients of PPP with different end groups and their respective sums in terms of that of their starting units have been developed and presented in the forms of transfer matrix.

PPP with different end groups and their mirror fragments

Linear poly(*p*-phenylenes) that are considered here have the general formula, $R_1-(C_6H_4)_{N_r}-R_2$ as shown in Fig. 1, with different end groups R_1 and R_2 such that (+) mirror fragments²⁹⁻³¹ of $R_1-(C_6H_4)_{N_r}-R_2$ are always alternant edge weighted linear chains. Thus the end group(s) R_s ($s = 1, 2$) can be hydrogen, methylene, allyl, pentadienyl, etc. and hence PPPs can be shown to be obtained by taking several combinations of R_s ($s = 1, 2$); such as PPP (Fig. 2(a)), 1-methylene PPP (Fig. 2(b)) and 1,1'-dimethylene PPP (Fig. 2(c)), 1-allyl PPP (Fig. 2(d)), 1-methylene 1'-allyl PPP (Fig. 3(a)) and 1,1'-bisallyl PPP (Fig. 3(b)), 1-pentadienyl PPP (Fig. 3(c)), 1-methylene 1'-pentadienyl PPP (Fig. 3(d)), 1-allyl 1'-pentadienyl PPP (Fig. 4(a)), 1,1'-bis-pentadienyl PPP (Fig. 4(b)), etc.

Algorithm for characteristic polynomials

A representative PPP graph with end groups R_1 and R_2 shown in Fig. 1 when subjected to the symmetry plane fragmentation²⁹⁻³¹ each gets decomposed into an alternant edge weighted $(\sqrt{2}, 1)$ linear chain and ethylene units and/or isolated vertex or vertices depending on the end group(s) R_s ($s = 1, 2$) present in the PPP with n_{R_s} number of vertices for each R_s .

Let us focus our attention first to the (+) mirror fragment²⁹⁻³¹. The length or the number of edges of the alternant edge weighted linear chain so obtained are $(4N_r + n_{R_1}^+ + n_{R_2}^+)$, where $n_{R_1}^+$ and $n_{R_2}^+$ are the number of vertices of R_1 and R_2 respectively that belong to the (+) mirror fragments²⁹⁻³¹. For the end groups (R_s) of hydrogen, methylene, allyl and pentadienyl, the values of $n_{R_s}^+$ are 0, 1, 2 and 3 respectively. In case of alternant edge weighted (k_1, k_2) linear chains of N vertices the expression for the CP has recently been derived¹⁶,

$$a_{2j}^{(N)} = (k_1^2 + k_2^2)a_{2(j-1)}^{(N-2)} + a_{2j}^{(N-2)} - k_1^2 k_2^2 a_{2(j-2)}^{(N-4)} \quad (2)$$

The CP coefficients are found to be dependent on values of k_1 and k_2 but not on their sequence in the chain as evident from the eq. (2). Putting the alternant edge weights $(\sqrt{2}, 1)$ or $(1, \sqrt{2})$ instead of (k_1, k_2) in eq. (2) we can get the following expression of the CP coefficients for any such system having $(4N_r + n_{R_1}^+ + n_{R_2}^+)$

Fig. 1. End group-graph (R_1-R_2), starting unit graph ($G(SU)$) and a PPP graph with different end groups R_1 and R_2 along with its symmetry plane fragmentation.

Fig. 2. (a) PPP graph (G_1), its end groups-graph (null-vertex graph) and starting unit graph ($G_1(SU)$); (b) 1-methylene PPP, its end group-graph (methylene) and starting unit graph ($G_2(SU)$); (c) 1,1'-dimethylene PPP, its end group-graph (ethylene) and starting unit graph ($G_3(SU)$) and (d) 1-allyl PPP, its end group-graph (allyl) and the starting unit graph ($G_4(SU)$).

number of vertices,

$$\begin{aligned}
 a_{2j}^{(4N_r + n_{R_1}^+ + n_{R_2}^+)} &= 3a_{2(j-1)}^{(4N_r - 2 + n_{R_1}^+ + n_{R_2}^+)} \\
 + a_{2j}^{(4N_r - 2 + n_{R_1}^+ + n_{R_2}^+)} &- 2a_{2(j-2)}^{(4N_r - 4 + n_{R_1}^+ + n_{R_2}^+)} \quad (3)
 \end{aligned}$$

Now for a given set of end groups the starting unit of a

given PPP polymer can be generated by inserting hexagonal rings in between the end groups, and then by increasing hexagonal rings one by one, one arrive at the desired PPP polymer. Thus to express the CP coefficients of a given PPP in terms that of its starting unit one needs to modify the eq. (3) in such a way that all the coefficients are for edge weighted linear chains having

Fig. 3. (a) 1-Methylene, 1'-allyl PPP (G_5), its end group-graph (trimethylenemethene) and starting unit graph ($G_5(SU)$); (b) 1,1'-bisallyl PPP (G_6), its end group-graph (bisallyl) and the starting unit graph ($G_6(SU)$); (c) 1-pentadienyl PPP (G_7), its end group-graph (pentadienyl) and the starting unit graph ($G_7(SU)$) and (d) 1-methylene 1'-pentadienyl PPP (G_8), its end group-graph (3-methylene pentadienyl) and the starting unit graph ($G_8(SU)$).

vertices (excluding of $(n_{R_1}^+ + n_{R_2}^+)$) in the multiple of 4. With some simple algebra the eq. (3) can be modified to the required form

$$a_{2j}^{(4N_r + n_{R_1}^+ + n_{R_2}^+)} = a_{2j}^{(4(N_r - 1) + n_{R_1}^+ + n_{R_2}^+)} +$$

$$6a_{2j-2}^{(4(N_r - 1) + n_{R_1}^+ + n_{R_2}^+)} + 5a_{2j-4}^{(4(N_r - 1) + n_{R_1}^+ + n_{R_2}^+)}$$

$$-4a_{2j-8}^{(4(N_r - 2) + n_{R_1}^+ + n_{R_2}^+)} \quad (4)$$

Fig. 4. (a) 1-Allyl, 1'-pentadienyl PPP (G_9), its end group-graph (allylpentadienyl) and starting unit graph ($G_9(SU)$); (b) 1,1'- bispentadienyl PPP (G_{10}), its end group-graph (bispentadienyl) and the starting unit graph ($G_6(SU)$).

In the (-) mirror fragments²⁹⁻³¹ the total number of ethylene units (K_2 graphs) so obtained for such a PPP of N_r number of hexagonal rings will be $(N_r + m_{R_1}^- + m_{R_2}^-)$, where $m_{R_s}^-$ is the number of K_2 graph obtained as (-) mirror fragment²⁹⁻³¹ from R_s and is one for pentadienyl group but zero for the rest of the groups considered here. The CP coefficients for $(N_r + m_{R_1}^- + m_{R_2}^-)$ ethylene units (K_2 graphs) can be expressed as

$$a_{2j}^{2(N_r + m_{R_1}^- + m_{R_2}^-)} = N_r + m_{R_1}^- + m_{R_2}^- C_j$$

$$= (N_r + m_{R_1}^- + m_{R_2}^-)! / j!(N_r + m_{R_1}^- + m_{R_2}^- - j)! \quad (5)$$

If R_s is an allyl group, the (-) mirror fragment²⁹⁻³¹ of the concerned PPP contains isolated vertex for each of R_s present and in this case the values of the CP coefficients will not change. So for the calculation of the CP coefficients of such graph one needs to combine the CP of the (+) mirror fragment and the CP of the (-) mirror fragments²⁹⁻³¹.

CP coefficients in the form of recurrence relation :

Thus combining the eqs. (4) and (5) we have

$$a_{2j}^{(6N_r + n_{R_1} + n_{R_2})} =$$

$$\sum_{l=0}^{N_r + m_{R_1}^- + m_{R_2}^-} N_r + m_{R_1}^- + m_{R_2}^- C_l a_{2j-2l}^{(4N_r + n_{R_1}^+ + n_{R_2}^+)}$$

$$= \sum_{l=0}^{N_r + m_{R_1}^- + m_{R_2}^-} N_r + m_{R_1}^- + m_{R_2}^- C_l \left[a_{2j}^{(4(N_r - 1) + n_{R_1}^+ + n_{R_2}^+)} \right.$$

$$+ 6a_{2j-2}^{(4(N_r - 1) + n_{R_1}^+ + n_{R_2}^+)} + 5a_{2j-4}^{(4(N_r - 1) + n_{R_1}^+ + n_{R_2}^+)}$$

$$\left. - 4a_{2j-8}^{(4(N_r - 2) + n_{R_1}^+ + n_{R_2}^+)} \right]$$

$$= a_{2j}^{(6(N_r - 1) + n_{R_1} + n_{R_2})} + 7a_{2j-2}^{(6(N_r - 1) + n_{R_1} + n_{R_2})}$$

$$+ 11a_{2j-4}^{(6(N_r - 1) + n_{R_1} + n_{R_2})} + 5a_{2j-6}^{(6(N_r - 1) + n_{R_1} + n_{R_2})}$$

$$- 4 \left(a_{2j-8}^{(6(N_r - 2) + n_{R_1} + n_{R_2})} + 2a_{2j-10}^{(6(N_r - 2) + n_{R_1} + n_{R_2})} \right. \quad (6)$$

$$\left. + a_{2j-12}^{(6(N_r - 2) + n_{R_1} + n_{R_2})} \right)$$

The eq. (6) is the recurrence relation for the CP coefficients of a PPP with N_r number of hexagonal rings in terms of the preceding PPPs with (N_r-1) and (N_r-2) number of hexagonal rings.

CP coefficients in the form of matrix product :

This eq. (6) can conveniently be expressed in matrix product form

$$a_{2j}^{(6N_r + n_{R_1} + n_{R_2})} = (1 \ 7 \ 11 \ 5) \begin{pmatrix} a_{2j}^{(6(N_r-1) + n_{R_1} + n_{R_2})} \\ a_{2j-2}^{(6(N_r-1) + n_{R_1} + n_{R_2})} \\ a_{2j-4}^{(6(N_r-1) + n_{R_1} + n_{R_2})} \\ a_{2j-6}^{(6(N_r-1) + n_{R_1} + n_{R_2})} \end{pmatrix} - 4(1 \ 2 \ 1) \begin{pmatrix} a_{2j-8}^{(6(N_r-2) + n_{R_1} + n_{R_2})} \\ a_{2j-10}^{(6(N_r-2) + n_{R_1} + n_{R_2})} \\ a_{2j-12}^{(6(N_r-2) + n_{R_1} + n_{R_2})} \end{pmatrix} = \mathbf{Aa} - \mathbf{Bb} \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{A}$, $\mathbf{B}$ are row matrices and $\mathbf{a}$, $\mathbf{b}$ are column matrices as

$$\mathbf{A} = (1 \ 7 \ 11 \ 5), \mathbf{a} = \begin{pmatrix} a_{2j}^{(6(N_r-1) + n_{R_1} + n_{R_2})} \\ a_{2j-2}^{(6(N_r-1) + n_{R_1} + n_{R_2})} \\ a_{2j-4}^{(6(N_r-1) + n_{R_1} + n_{R_2})} \\ a_{2j-6}^{(6(N_r-1) + n_{R_1} + n_{R_2})} \end{pmatrix},$$

$$\mathbf{B} = 4(1 \ 2 \ 1) \text{ and } \mathbf{b} = \begin{pmatrix} a_{2j-8}^{(6(N_r-2) + n_{R_1} + n_{R_2})} \\ a_{2j-10}^{(6(N_r-2) + n_{R_1} + n_{R_2})} \\ a_{2j-12}^{(6(N_r-2) + n_{R_1} + n_{R_2})} \end{pmatrix}$$

The eq. (7) is a recurrence relation but in matrix product form. Here it is important to note that a coefficient will be zero if its subscript exceeds the superscript or any of

them is negative and a coefficient will be unity if the subscript is zero or both the subscript and superscript are zero.

Illustration of the calculation of CP coefficients for PPP

In case of PPP ((Fig. 1(a))) with no end group $n_{R_1} = n_{R_2} = 0$ the above eq. (7) takes the form

$$a_{2j}^{(6N_r)} = \mathbf{Aa} - \mathbf{Bb} \quad (8)$$

with the values of $\mathbf{a}$ and $\mathbf{b}$

$$\mathbf{a} = \begin{pmatrix} a_{2j}^{(6(N_r-1))} \\ a_{2j-2}^{(6(N_r-1))} \\ a_{2j-4}^{(6(N_r-1))} \\ a_{2j-6}^{(6(N_r-1))} \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

$$\mathbf{b} = \begin{pmatrix} a_{2j-8}^{(6(N_r-2))} \\ a_{2j-10}^{(6(N_r-2))} \\ a_{2j-12}^{(6(N_r-2))} \end{pmatrix} \quad (10)$$

The CP coefficients of the repeating unit i.e. of benzene are well known and are given as

$$a_0^{(6)} = 1, a_2^{(6)} = 6, a_4^{(6)} = 9 \text{ and } a_6^{(6)} = 4 \quad (11)$$

Let us evaluate the CP coefficients of biphenyl, for which the eqs. (8-10) get reduced to

$$a_{2j}^{(12)} = \mathbf{Aa} - \mathbf{Bb} \quad (12)$$

$$\mathbf{a} = \begin{pmatrix} a_{2j}^{(6)} \\ a_{2j-2}^{(6)} \\ a_{2j-4}^{(6)} \\ a_{2j-6}^{(6)} \end{pmatrix} \quad (13)$$

$$\mathbf{b} = \begin{pmatrix} a_{2j-8}^{(0)} \\ a_{2j-10}^{(0)} \\ a_{2j-12}^{(0)} \end{pmatrix} \quad (14)$$

Here the elements of matrix **a** are the CP coefficients of benzene and the elements of matrix **b** are the CP coefficients of a null graph.

Now putting different *j* values ranging 0 to $N_r/2$, i.e. 0 to 6, in eq. (12), the calculation of the CP coefficients of biphenyl is illustrated with the use of eqs. (11)–(14) as follows.

$$a_0^{(12)} = (1 \ 7 \ 11 \ 5) \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} - 4(1 \ 2 \ 1) \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = 1$$

$$a_0^{(12)} = (1 \ 7 \ 11 \ 5) \begin{pmatrix} 6 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} - 4(1 \ 2 \ 1) \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = 13$$

$$a_0^{(12)} = (1 \ 7 \ 11 \ 5) \begin{pmatrix} 9 \\ 6 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} - 4(1 \ 2 \ 1) \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = 62$$

$$a_0^{(12)} = (1 \ 7 \ 11 \ 5) \begin{pmatrix} 4 \\ 9 \\ 6 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} - 4(1 \ 2 \ 1) \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = 138$$

$$a_0^{(12)} = (1 \ 7 \ 11 \ 5) \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 4 \\ 9 \\ 6 \end{pmatrix} - 4(1 \ 2 \ 1) \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = 153$$

$$a_0^{(12)} = (1 \ 7 \ 11 \ 5) \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 4 \\ 9 \end{pmatrix} - 4(1 \ 2 \ 1) \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = 81$$

$$a_0^{(12)} = (1 \ 7 \ 11 \ 5) \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 4 \end{pmatrix} - 4(1 \ 2 \ 1) \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = 16$$

All these CP coefficients of biphenyl so obtained are needed to evaluate the CP coefficients of *p*-triphenylene, which

in turn are needed for the calculation of CP coefficients of *p*-tetraphenylene, and so on. In the same way knowing the CP coefficients of the starting unit one can calculate the CP coefficients of the corresponding PPP of varying hexagonal rings.

CP in the form of recurrence relation :

The eq. (7) results in the following recursive relation for the CP of such PPP

$$P_{N_r}(G;x) = (x^6 - 7x^4 + 11x^2 - 5)P_{N_r-1}(G;x) - 4(x^2 - 1)^2 P_{N_r-2}(G;x) \quad (15)$$

This expression is same as was given by Dias³² following from the algorithm developed by Hosoya *et al.*³³ using rotational symmetry. But in this study we arrived at this formula using plane of symmetry followed by combining the CPs of the mirror fragments for arriving at the CP of the original graph.

CP in the form of transfer matrix :

Transfer matrix is a valuable tool and is found to be used in several occasions for solving physicochemical problems^{34–36}. The eq. (15) is a recurrence relation but can be an analytical form when transfer matrix is used as

$$\begin{pmatrix} P_{N_r}(G;x) \\ P_{N_r-1}(G;x) \end{pmatrix} = \mathbf{T} \begin{pmatrix} P_{N_r-1}(G;x) \\ P_{N_r-2}(G;x) \end{pmatrix} \quad (16)$$

where

$$\mathbf{T} = \begin{pmatrix} (x^6 - 7x^4 + 11x^2 - 5) & -4(x^2 - 1)^2 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (17)$$

is called the transfer matrix for this case.

The eq. (16) can be written as

$$\begin{pmatrix} P_{N_r}(G;x) \\ P_{N_r-1}(G;x) \end{pmatrix} = \mathbf{T}^{(N_r-1)} \begin{pmatrix} P_1(G;x) \\ P_0(G;x) \end{pmatrix} \quad (18)$$

where $P_1(G;x)$ is the CP of the starting unit i.e. of R_1 –(C_6H_4)– R_2 and $P_0(G;x)$ is the CP of R_1 – R_2 . For simple PPP both R_1 and R_2 are hydrogen and hence, $P_0(G;x) = 1$. Similarly for PPP with R_1 and R_1 are hydrogen and methylene groups respectively, $P_0(G;x)$ is x , for PPP with both R_1 and R_2 are methylene group, $P_0(G;x)$ for such system is $x^2 - 1$, and so on.

CP coefficients in analytical form :

The eq. (7) can be exploited to yield analytical formula for the CP coefficients of such PPPs. For doing this let us write down the eq. (6) in the form

$$a_{2j}^{(6N_r+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} = \sum_{k=0}^3 A_{2k}^{(6(N_r-1)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})}$$

$$a_{2j-2k}^{(6(N_r-1)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})}$$

$$- \sum_{k=0}^2 B_{2k}^{(6(N_r-2)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} a_{2j-8-2k}^{(6(N_r-2)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} \quad (19)$$

For $N_r = 1$,

$$A_0^{(6(N_r-1)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} = a_0^{(6+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})},$$

$$A_2^{(6(N_r-1)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} = a_2^{(6+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})},$$

$$A_4^{(6(N_r-1)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} = a_4^{(6+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})},$$

$$A_6^{(6(N_r-1)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} = a_6^{(6+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} \quad (20)$$

and all B s are set to zero.

Whereas for $N_r \geq 2$,

$$A_0^{(6(N_r-1)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} = 1, A_2^{(6(N_r-1)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} = 7,$$

$$A_4^{(6(N_r-1)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} = 11,$$

$$A_6^{(6(N_r-1)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} = 5 \quad (21)$$

$$B_0^{(6(N_r-2)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} = 4, B_2^{(6(N_r-2)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} = 8,$$

$$B_4^{(6(N_r-2)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} = 4 \quad (22)$$

with all A having subscripts greater than 6 are set to zero and all B having subscripts greater than 4 are set to zero.

First step of reduction of the eq. (19) results in the CP coefficients in terms of that of PPP having (N_r-2) , (N_r-3) and (N_r-4) number of hexagonal rings as

$$a_{2j}^{(6N_r+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} = \sum_{l_2=0}^6 \sum_{l_1=0}^{l_2} A_{2l_1}^{(6(N_r-1)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})}$$

$$A_{2l_2-2l_1}^{(6(N_r-2)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} a_{2j-2l_2}^{(6(N_r-2)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} +$$

$$\sum_{k_2=0}^4 \sum_{k_1=0}^{k_2} B_{2k_1}^{(6(N_r-2)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} B_{2k_2-2k_1}^{(6(N_r-4)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} a_{2j-8-2k_2}^{(6(N_r-4)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})}$$

$$- \sum_{l_1=0}^3 \sum_{k_1=0}^2 A_{2l_1}^{(6(N_r-1)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} B_{2k_1}^{(6(N_r-3)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} a_{2j-8-2(l_1+k_1)}^{(6(N_r-3)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})}$$

$$- \sum_{l_1=0}^3 \sum_{k_1=0}^2 A_{2l_1}^{(6(N_r-3)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} B_{2k_1}^{(6(N_r-2)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} a_{2j-8-2(l_1+k_1)}^{(6(N_r-3)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} \quad (23)$$

Proceeding step by step reduction one can finally arrive at the expression of CP coefficients of such a PPP having N_r hexagonal rings in terms of that of the starting unit as

$$a_{2j}^{(6N_r+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} =$$

$$\sum_{l_{N_r-1}=0}^{3(N_r-1)} \dots \sum_{l_3=0}^{l_4} \sum_{l_2=0}^{l_3} \sum_{l_1=0}^{l_2} A_{2l_1}^{(6(N_r-1)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} A_{2l_2-2l_1}^{(6(N_r-2)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} A_{2l_3-2l_2}^{(6(N_r-3)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} \dots A_{2l_{N_r-1}-2l_{N_r-2}}^{(6+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} a_{2j-2l_{N_r-1}}^{(6+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} -$$

$$\sum_{l_{N_r-2}, k_{N_r-2}=0}^{3(N_r-2), 2(N_r-2)} \dots \sum_{l_3, k_3=0}^{l_3, k_3} \sum_{l_2, k_2=0}^{l_2, k_2} A_{2l_1}^{(6(N_r-1)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} B_{2k_1}^{(6(N_r-3)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} \dots A_{2l_{N_r-2}-2l_{N_r-3}}^{(12+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} B_{2k_{N_r-2}-2k_{N_r-3}}^{(n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} a_{2j-8-2(k_{N_r-2}+l_{N_r-2})}^{(n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})}$$

$$- \sum_{l_{N_r-2}, k_{N_r-2}=0}^{3(N_r-2), 2(N_r-2)} \dots \sum_{l_2, k_2=0}^{l_3, k_3} \sum_{l_1, k_1=0}^{l_2, k_2} A_{2l_1}^{(6(N_r-3)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} B_{2k_1}^{(6(N_r-2)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} \dots A_{2l_{N_r-2}-2l_{N_r-3}}^{(n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} B_{2k_{N_r-2}-2k_{N_r-3}}^{(6+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} a_{2j-8-2(k_{N_r-2}+l_{N_r-2})}^{(n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} \quad (24)$$

Here j value ranges from 0 to $6N_r/2$ for $n_{R_1} + n_{R_2} = 0, 1$; from 0 to $(6N_r+2)/2$ for $n_{R_1} + n_{R_2} = 2, 3$; from 0 to $(6N_r+4)/2$ for $n_{R_1} + n_{R_2} = 4, 5$; from 0 to $(6N_r+6)/2$ for $n_{R_1} + n_{R_2} = 6$; from 0 to $(6N_r+8)/2$ for $n_{R_1} + n_{R_2} = 8$; from 0 to $(6N_r+10)/2$ for $n_{R_1} + n_{R_2} = 10$.

Illustration with triphenyl

In case of triphenyl the above eq. (24) takes the form

$$a_{2j}^{(18)} = \sum_{l_2=0}^6 \sum_{l_1=0}^{l_2} A_{2l_1}^{(12)} A_{2l_2-2l_1}^{(6)} a_{2j-2l_2}^{(6)} - 2 \sum_{l_1, k_1=0}^{3, 2} A_{2l_1}^{(12)} B_{2k_1}^{(0)} a_{2j-8-2(l_1+k_1)}^{(0)} - 2 \sum_{l_1, k_1=0}^{3, 2} A_{2l_1}^{(0)} B_{2k_1}^{(6)} a_{2j-8-2(l_1+k_1)}^{(0)} \quad (25)$$

which on summing over of all the summation indices results in

$$a_{2j}^{(18)} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} A_0^{(12)} A_0^{(6)} a_{2j}^{(6)} + (A_0^{(12)} A_2^{(6)} \\ + A_2^{(12)} A_0^{(6)}) a_{2j-2}^{(6)} \\ + (A_0^{(12)} A_4^{(6)} + A_2^{(12)} A_2^{(6)} \\ + A_4^{(12)} A_0^{(6)}) a_{2j-4}^{(6)} \\ + (A_0^{(12)} A_6^{(6)} + A_2^{(12)} A_4^{(6)} \\ + A_4^{(12)} A_2^{(6)} + A_6^{(12)} A_0^{(6)}) a_{2j-6}^{(6)} \\ + (A_0^{(12)} A_8^{(6)} + A_2^{(12)} A_6^{(6)} \\ + A_4^{(12)} A_4^{(6)} + A_6^{(12)} A_2^{(6)} \\ + A_8^{(12)} A_0^{(6)}) a_{2j-8}^{(6)} \\ + (A_0^{(12)} A_{10}^{(6)} + A_2^{(12)} A_8^{(6)} \\ + A_4^{(12)} A_6^{(6)} + A_6^{(12)} A_4^{(6)} \\ + A_8^{(12)} A_2^{(6)} + A_{10}^{(12)} A_0^{(6)}) a_{2j-10}^{(6)} \\ + (A_0^{(12)} A_{12}^{(6)} + A_2^{(12)} A_{10}^{(6)} \\ + A_4^{(12)} A_8^{(6)} + A_6^{(12)} A_6^{(6)} \\ + A_8^{(12)} A_4^{(6)} + A_{10}^{(12)} A_2^{(6)} \\ + A_{12}^{(12)} A_0^{(6)}) a_{2j-12}^{(6)} \end{array} \right\} - \left\{ \begin{array}{l} A_0^{(12)} B_0^{(0)} a_{2j-8}^{(0)} + (A_2^{(12)} B_0^{(0)} \\ + A_0^{(12)} B_2^{(0)}) a_{2j-10}^{(0)} + (A_4^{(12)} B_0^{(0)} \\ + A_2^{(12)} B_2^{(0)} + A_0^{(12)} B_4^{(0)}) a_{2j-12}^{(0)} \\ + (A_6^{(12)} B_0^{(0)} + A_4^{(12)} B_2^{(0)} \\ + A_2^{(12)} B_4^{(0)}) a_{2j-14}^{(0)} + (A_6^{(12)} B_2^{(0)} \\ + A_4^{(12)} B_4^{(0)}) a_{2j-16}^{(0)} + A_6^{(12)} B_4^{(0)} a_{2j-18}^{(0)} \end{array} \right\} - \left\{ \begin{array}{l} A_0^{(0)} B_0^{(6)} a_{2j-8}^{(0)} + (A_2^{(0)} B_0^{(6)} \\ + A_0^{(0)} B_2^{(6)}) a_{2j-10}^{(0)} + (A_4^{(0)} B_0^{(6)} \\ + A_2^{(0)} B_2^{(6)} + A_0^{(0)} B_4^{(6)}) a_{2j-12}^{(0)} \\ + (A_6^{(0)} B_0^{(6)} + A_4^{(0)} B_2^{(6)} \\ + A_2^{(0)} B_4^{(6)}) a_{2j-14}^{(0)} + (A_6^{(0)} B_2^{(6)} \\ + A_4^{(0)} B_4^{(6)}) a_{2j-16}^{(0)} \\ + A_6^{(0)} B_4^{(6)} a_{2j-18}^{(0)} \end{array} \right\} \quad (26)$$

Now putting different j values ranging from 0 to $6N_r/2 = 9$ we can obtain the CP coefficients for triphenyl as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
 a_0^{(18)} &= A_0^{(12)} A_0^{(6)} a_0^{(6)} = 1 \\
 a_0^{(18)} &= \{A_0^{(12)} A_0^{(6)} a_2^{(6)} + (A_0^{(12)} A_0^{(6)} + A_2^{(12)} A_0^{(6)}) a_0^{(6)}\} \\
 &= 6 + 2 \times 7 = 20 \\
 a_4^{(18)} &= \{A_0^{(12)} A_0^{(6)} a_4^{(6)} + (A_0^{(12)} A_2^{(6)} + A_2^{(12)} A_0^{(6)}) a_2^{(6)} \\
 &+ (A_0^{(12)} A_4^{(6)} + A_2^{(12)} A_2^{(6)} + A_4^{(6)} A_0^{(6)}) a_0^{(6)}\} \\
 &= 9 + 84 + 22 + 49 = 164
 \end{aligned}$$

$$a_6^{(18)} = \left\{ \begin{aligned} &A_0^{(12)} A_0^{(6)} a_6^{(6)} + (A_0^{(12)} A_2^{(6)} \\ &+ A_2^{(12)} A_0^{(6)}) a_4^{(6)} + (A_0^{(12)} A_4^{(6)} \\ &+ A_2^{(12)} A_2^{(6)} + A_4^{(6)} A_0^{(6)}) a_2^{(6)} \\ &+ (A_0^{(12)} A_6^{(6)} + A_2^{(12)} A_4^{(6)} + A_4^{(6)} A_2^{(6)} \\ &+ A_6^{(6)} A_0^{(6)}) a_0^{(6)} \end{aligned} \right\}$$

$$= \{4 + 126 + 426 + 164\} = 720$$

$$a_8^{(18)} = \left\{ \begin{aligned} &A_0^{(12)} A_0^{(6)} a_8^{(6)} + (A_0^{(12)} A_2^{(6)} + A_2^{(12)} A_0^{(6)}) a_6^{(6)} \\ &+ (A_0^{(12)} A_4^{(6)} + A_2^{(12)} A_2^{(6)} + A_4^{(6)} A_0^{(6)}) a_4^{(6)} \\ &+ (A_0^{(12)} A_6^{(6)} + A_2^{(12)} A_4^{(6)} + A_4^{(6)} A_2^{(6)} \\ &+ A_6^{(6)} A_0^{(6)}) a_2^{(6)} + (A_0^{(12)} A_8^{(6)} + A_2^{(12)} A_6^{(6)} \\ &+ A_4^{(6)} A_4^{(6)} + A_6^{(6)} A_2^{(6)} + A_8^{(6)} A_0^{(6)}) a_0^{(6)} \\ &- A_0^{(12)} B_0^{(0)} a_0^{(0)} - A_0^{(0)} B_0^{(6)} a_0^{(0)} \end{aligned} \right\}$$

$$= \{0 + 56 + 639 + 984 + 191 - 4 - 4\} = 1862$$

$$a_{10}^{(18)} = \left\{ \begin{aligned} &A_0^{(12)} A_0^{(6)} a_{10}^{(6)} + (A_0^{(12)} A_2^{(6)} + A_2^{(12)} A_2^{(6)}) a_8^{(6)} \\ &+ (A_0^{(12)} A_4^{(6)} + A_2^{(12)} A_2^{(6)} + A_4^{(6)} A_0^{(6)}) a_6^{(6)} \\ &+ (A_0^{(12)} A_6^{(6)} + A_2^{(12)} A_4^{(6)} + A_4^{(6)} A_2^{(6)} \\ &+ A_6^{(6)} A_0^{(6)}) a_4^{(6)} + (A_0^{(12)} A_8^{(6)} \\ &+ A_2^{(12)} A_6^{(6)} + A_4^{(6)} A_4^{(6)} + A_6^{(6)} A_2^{(6)} \\ &+ A_8^{(6)} A_0^{(6)}) a_2^{(6)} + (A_0^{(12)} A_{10}^{(6)} \\ &+ A_2^{(12)} A_8^{(6)} + A_4^{(6)} A_6^{(6)} + A_6^{(6)} A_4^{(6)} \\ &+ A_8^{(6)} A_2^{(6)} + A_{10}^{(6)} A_0^{(6)}) a_0^{(6)} \\ &- A_0^{(12)} B_0^{(0)} a_2^{(0)} - (A_2^{(12)} B_0^{(0)} \\ &+ A_0^{(12)} B_2^{(0)}) a_0^{(0)} - A_0^{(0)} B_0^{(6)} a_2^{(0)} \\ &- (A_0^{(0)} B_2^{(6)} + A_2^{(0)} B_0^{(6)}) a_0^{(0)} \end{aligned} \right\}$$

$$= \{0 + 0 + 284 + 1476 + 1146 + 110 - 28 - 8 - 8 - 24\} = 2948$$

$$a_{12}^{(18)} = \left\{ \begin{aligned} &(A_0^{(12)} A_6^{(6)} + A_2^{(12)} A_4^{(6)} + A_4^{(12)} A_2^{(6)} \\ &+ A_6^{(12)} A_0^{(6)}) a_6^{(6)} + (A_0^{(12)} A_8^{(6)} \\ &+ A_2^{(12)} A_6^{(6)} + A_4^{(12)} A_4^{(6)} + A_6^{(12)} A_2^{(6)} \\ &+ A_8^{(12)} A_0^{(6)}) a_4^{(6)} + (A_0^{(12)} A_{10}^{(6)} \\ &+ A_2^{(12)} A_8^{(6)} + A_4^{(12)} A_6^{(6)} + A_6^{(12)} A_4^{(6)} \\ &+ A_8^{(12)} A_2^{(6)} + A_{10}^{(12)} A_0^{(6)}) a_2^{(6)} + \\ &(A_0^{(12)} A_{12}^{(6)} + A_2^{(12)} A_{10}^{(6)} + A_4^{(12)} A_8^{(6)} \\ &+ A_6^{(12)} A_6^{(6)} + A_8^{(12)} A_4^{(6)} + A_{10}^{(12)} A_2^{(6)} \\ &+ A_{12}^{(12)} A_0^{(6)}) a_0^{(6)} - (A_4^{(12)} B_0^{(0)} \\ &+ A_2^{(12)} B_2^{(0)} + A_0^{(12)} B_4^{(0)}) a_0^{(0)} \\ &- (A_4^{(0)} B_0^{(6)} + A_2^{(0)} B_2^{(6)} + A_0^{(0)} B_4^{(6)}) a_0^{(0)} \end{aligned} \right\}$$

$$= \{656 + 1719 + 660 + 25 - 104 - 88\} = 2868$$

$$a_{14}^{(18)} = \left\{ \begin{aligned} &(A_0^{(12)} A_8^{(6)} + A_2^{(12)} A_6^{(6)} + A_4^{(12)} A_4^{(6)} \\ &+ A_6^{(12)} A_2^{(6)} + A_8^{(12)} A_0^{(6)}) a_6^{(6)} \\ &+ (A_0^{(12)} A_{10}^{(6)} + A_2^{(12)} A_8^{(6)} \\ &+ A_4^{(12)} A_6^{(6)} + A_6^{(12)} A_4^{(6)} \\ &+ A_8^{(12)} A_2^{(6)} + A_{10}^{(12)} A_0^{(6)}) a_4^{(6)} \\ &+ (A_0^{(12)} A_{12}^{(6)} + A_2^{(12)} A_{10}^{(6)} \\ &+ A_4^{(12)} A_8^{(6)} + A_6^{(12)} A_6^{(6)} + A_8^{(12)} A_4^{(6)} \\ &+ A_{10}^{(12)} A_2^{(6)} + A_{12}^{(12)} A_0^{(6)}) a_2^{(6)} \\ &- (A_6^{(12)} B_0^{(0)} + A_4^{(12)} B_2^{(0)} \\ &+ A_2^{(12)} B_4^{(0)}) a_0^{(0)} - (A_6^{(0)} B_0^{(6)} \\ &+ A_4^{(0)} B_2^{(6)} + A_2^{(0)} B_4^{(6)}) a_0^{(0)} \end{aligned} \right\}$$

$$= \{764 + 990 + 150 - 136 - 112\} = 1656$$

$$a_{16}^{(18)} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} (A_0^{(12)} A_{10}^{(6)} + A_2^{(12)} A_8^{(6)}) \\ + A_4^{(12)} A_6^{(6)} + A_6^{(12)} A_4^{(6)} \\ + A_8^{(12)} A_2^{(6)} + A_{10}^{(12)} A_0^{(6)} a_6^{(6)} \\ + (A_0^{(12)} A_{12}^{(6)} + A_2^{(12)} A_{10}^{(6)}) \\ + A_4^{(12)} A_8^{(6)} + A_6^{(12)} A_6^{(6)} \\ + A_8^{(12)} A_4^{(6)} + A_{10}^{(12)} A_2^{(6)} \\ + A_{12}^{(12)} A_0^{(6)} a_4^{(6)} - (A_6^{(12)} B_2^{(0)}) \\ + A_4^{(12)} B_4^{(0)} a_0^{(0)} - (A_6^{(0)} B_2^{(6)}) \\ + A_4^{(0)} B_4^{(6)} a_0^{(0)} \end{array} \right\}$$

$$= \{440 + 225 - 84 - 68\} = 513$$

$$a_{18}^{(18)} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} (A_0^{(12)} A_{12}^{(6)} + A_2^{(12)} A_{10}^{(6)}) \\ + A_4^{(12)} A_8^{(6)} + A_6^{(12)} A_6^{(6)} \\ + A_8^{(12)} A_4^{(6)} + A_{10}^{(12)} A_2^{(6)} \\ + A_{12}^{(12)} A_0^{(6)} a_6^{(6)} \\ - A_6^{(12)} B_4^{(0)} a_0^{(0)} - A_6^{(0)} B_4^{(6)} a_0^{(0)} \end{array} \right\}$$

$$= 100 - 20 - 16 = 64$$

Sum of CP coefficients (Z')

Hosoya index, a well studied topological index, is

defined^{37,38} as $Z = Z(G) = \sum_{k=0}^{N/2} m(G,k)$ where $m(G,k)$ is

the number of k -matchings and is the k -th coefficient of the matching polynomial (MP) of a graph G . A k -matching of G is a selection of k mutually independent edges (i.e. the edges that are not incident on a common vertex) of G . Whereas a CP coefficient can be obtained from the respective MP coefficient just by incorporating the contribution of ring(s) present in the graph. In case of tree the characteristic polynomial (CP) coefficients are equal to the corresponding matching polynomial coefficients^{2,3}. The sum of CP coefficients (Z'_{N_r}) is an important topological index which has recently been found¹⁶ to model physical properties such as ambient condition density and bulk modulus for PPP molecules having no end groups.

The sum of CP coefficients (Z'_{N_r}) can be expressed by summing both sides of eq. (6) over j , j ranging from 0 to Y ($Y = (6N_r + n_{R_1} + n_{R_2})/2$ for $n_{R_1} + n_{R_2}$ is even or $Y = (6N_r + n_{R_1} + n_{R_2} - 1)/2$ for $n_{R_1} + n_{R_2}$ is odd) as

$$Z'_{N_r} = \sum_{j=0}^Y a_{2j}^{(6N_r+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})}$$

$$= \sum_{j=0}^Y a_{2j}^{(6(N_r-1)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})}$$

$$+ 7 \sum_{j=0}^Y a_{2j-2}^{(6(N_r-1)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})}$$

$$+ 11 \sum_{j=0}^Y a_{2j-4}^{(6(N_r-1)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})}$$

$$+ 5 \sum_{j=0}^Y a_{2j-6}^{(6(N_r-1)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})}$$

$$- 4 \left(\begin{array}{l} \sum_{j=0}^Y a_{2j-8}^{(6(N_r-2)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} \\ + 2 \sum_{j=0}^Y a_{2j-10}^{(6(N_r-2)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} \\ + \sum_{j=0}^Y a_{2j-12}^{(6(N_r-2)+n_{R_1}+n_{R_2})} \end{array} \right)$$

$$= Z'_{N_r-1} + 7Z'_{N_r-1} + 11Z'_{N_r-1} + 5Z'_{N_r-1}$$

$$- 4(Z'_{N_r-2} + 2Z'_{N_r-2} + Z'_{N_r-2})$$

$$= 24Z'_{N_r-1} - 16Z'_{N_r-2} \tag{27}$$

The eq. (27) is a recurrence relation and is found to be same as derived in our earlier work¹⁶.

Sum of the CP coefficients in the form of matrix product :

The eq. (27) can be expressed in a matrix product form as

$$Z'_{N_r} = \mathbf{QZ}' \tag{28}$$

$$\text{where } \mathbf{S} = (24-16) \text{ and } \mathbf{Z}' = \begin{pmatrix} Z'_{N_r-1} \\ Z'_{N_r-2} \end{pmatrix} \tag{29}$$

Illustration for the calculation of the sum of CP coefficients

Let us illustrate the calculation of the sum of CP coefficients for any one of such PPP say PPP having no end group(s). For such PPP we need the sums of CP coefficients of biphenyl and triphenyl (e.g. Z_2 and Z_3 that are 20 and 464 respectively) in order to calculate that for the higher analogues, for example, the sum of CP coefficients of terphenyl, $Z_4 = (24-16) \binom{464}{20} = 10816$, that of

pentaphenyl, $Z_5 = (24-16) \binom{10816}{464} = 25216$ and so on.

Similarly for any such PPPs having end group(s) just knowing the sum of the CP coefficients of the preceding two PPP one can calculate the sum of the CP coefficients of with increase in the number of hexagonal rings in a given kind.

Sum of CP coefficients in the form of transfer matrix :

The eq. (27) can easily be expressed in transfer matrix form as

$$\begin{pmatrix} Z'_{N_r} \\ Z'_{N_r-1} \end{pmatrix} = \mathbf{T} \begin{pmatrix} Z'_{N_r-1} \\ Z'_{N_r-2} \end{pmatrix} \quad (30)$$

where,

$$\mathbf{T} = \begin{pmatrix} 24 & -16 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (31)$$

is called the transfer matrix in this case.

The eq. (30) ultimately results in

$$\begin{pmatrix} Z'_{N_r} \\ Z'_{N_r-1} \end{pmatrix} = \mathbf{T}^{(N_r-1)} \begin{pmatrix} Z'_1 \\ Z'_0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (32)$$

where Z'_1 and Z'_0 are the sums of the CP coefficients for the starting unit and the null graph respectively.

For $n_{R_1} + n_{R_2} = 0$, the starting unit is benzene (Fig. 1(a)) with $Z'_1 = 20$ and $Z'_0 = 1$; for $n_{R_1} + n_{R_2} = 1$, the starting unit is 1-methylenebenzene (Fig. 1(b)) with $Z'_1 = 28$ and $Z'_0 = 0$, for $n_{R_1} + n_{R_2} = 2$, the starting unit is *p*-dimethylenebenzene (Fig. 1(c)) with $Z'_1 = 40$ and $Z'_0 = 2$ for each of the three cases. For all other PPPs, Z'_0 is the

sum of CP coefficients of the respective end group-graph.

Illustration with PPP having no end group(s)

Let us illustrate this eq. (32) for the calculation of Z'_{N_r} for any one such PPP discussed here, say PPP having no end group. For a sample calculation, let us consider a PPP graph having number of hexagonal rings, $N_r = 4$. Thus putting $N_r = 4$ in the above eq. (32) and taking the values of $Z'_1 = 20$ and $Z'_0 = 1$, we have

$$\begin{pmatrix} Z'_4 \\ Z'_3 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 24 & -16 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}^3 \begin{pmatrix} Z'_1 \\ Z'_0 \end{pmatrix} \\ = \begin{pmatrix} 13056 & -8960 \\ 560 & -384 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 20 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 252160 \\ 10816 \end{pmatrix}$$

From the transform matrix given in eq. (32) one can see that the sum of the CP coefficients of the starting unit is sufficient for calculation of the same for any of its higher analogues of the given kind.

The eigenspectra of $\mathbf{T}$ given in eq. (31) is obtained by solving the equation, $\lambda^2 - 24\lambda + 16 = 0$ and is found to be $12 \pm 8\sqrt{2}$. Hence Z'_{N_r} can be expressed as

$$Z'_{N_r} = \{c_1(12 + 8\sqrt{2})^{N_r} + \{c_2(12 - 8\sqrt{2})^{N_r}\} \quad (33)$$

where c_1 and c_2 can be obtained by putting the values Z'_{N_r} for $N_r = 0, 1$ and subsequently solving eq. (33). Neglecting the second term in the RHS of eq. (33) owing to its low value, Z'_{N_r} could be approximated to $Z'_{N_r} \approx c_1(12 + 8\sqrt{2})^{N_r}$, which indicates that $\log(Z'_{N_r})$ is linearly dependent on N_r with same slope ($\sim \log(12 + 8\sqrt{2}) = 1.3676$) but of different intercepts, depending on the starting units. This justifies our observation of linear variation of ambient condition densities and bulk modulus with $\log(Z'_{N_r})$ and is in agreement with the work of Heimel *et al.* In case PPP (G_1) with no end group (Fig. 2) the values of c_1 and c_2 are found to be 0.8536 and 0.1464 respectively and hence the above eq. (33) becomes,

$$Z'_{N_r} = \{(0.8536)(12 + 8\sqrt{2})^{N_r} \\ + (0.1464)(12 - 8\sqrt{2})^{N_r}\} \\ \approx (0.8536)(12 + 8\sqrt{2})^{N_r} \quad (34)$$

Conclusion

The algorithm developed here is convenient to obtain the characteristic polynomial of PPP once the CP of the starting monomer unit is found to be expressed in the form of transfer matrix. A facile computer program can be made with such algorithm. The CP so obtained may be used to generate the eigenvalues that are important in molecular vibration analysis^{39,40}. CPs are important for obtaining many important results⁴¹ about total π -electron energy through the use of famous Coulson function^{42,43} for a wide variety of graphs²⁻⁴ ranging from small to large molecules like fullerenes. Such π -electron energies^{2,3} are still today considered as a good model for calculation of molecular energies. Besides these, characteristic polynomials have applications in chemical kinetics⁴⁴ and estimating opacity polynomials, vanishing of which dictates the zero conductance at a given energy for tight-binding source and sink potential (SSP) model of transmission in single molecule π -conjugated conductor^{26,27}. The molecules corresponding to the PPP graphs G_2 , G_4 (Fig. 2), G_5 , G_6 , G_7 (Fig. 3) and G_9 (Fig. 4) possess zero eigenvalue(s) in their eigenspectra as is evident from the mirror fragmentations, so these molecules with infinite number of rings possess conduction band adjacent to their respective valence bands and are predicted to be organic conductors^{4,45}. From the Fig. 1 it is seen that although all the graphs presented here are subspectral^{46,2,4} to each other but the graphs within brackets such as $\{G_1, G_4, G_6\}$, $\{G_2, G_5, G_7, G_9\}$ and $\{G_3, G_8, G_{10}\}$ in Figs. 2-4 are strongly isospectral^{46,2,4} as was shown by Dias^{32,47}. The CP coefficients, rather than eigenvalues of matrices, are of importance in quantum mechanical Monte-Carlo simulations^{48,49}.

The sum of CP coefficients (analogous to the Hosoya index^{37,38}) has been shown to be expressed in the form of transfer matrix and is subsequently used to show that the logarithm of the sum of the CP coefficients of any of the ten different types of PPP is linearly related to the number of hexagonal ring present in the respective PPP. The sum of CP coefficients can also be used as structure-property descriptor¹⁶.

Moreover the graphs considered here are novel π -conjugate organic molecules and are supposed to be promising candidates for low cost and easy processing materials for electro-optical and electronic applications¹⁸⁻²⁵. On

account of this, the work incorporated in the manuscript may have some importance.

Acknowledgement

Authors thank the University Grants Commission, New Delhi, for providing financial assistance extended through the CAS Project in the Department of Chemistry of the University of Burdwan.

References

1. D. M. Cvetković, M. Doob and H. Sachs, "Spectra of Graphs : Theory and Application", Academic Press, New York, 1979.
2. N. Trinajstić, "Chemical Graph Theory", CRC Press, Boca Raton, 1992.
3. I. Gutman and O. E. Polansky, "Mathematical Concepts in Organic Chemistry", Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1986.
4. J. R. Dias, "Molecular Orbital Calculations Using Chemical Graph Theory", Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1993.
5. H. Sachs, *Publ. Math. Debrecen*, 1964, **11**, 119.
6. A. Graovac, I. Gutman, N. Trinajstić and T. Zivković, *Theoret. Chim. Acta (Berl.)*, 1972, **26**, 67.
7. J. Buschen, Mémoire de Licence, Université Libre, de Bruxelles, 1974.
8. J. Brocas, D. Fastenakel, J. Hicquebrand and R. Willem, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belges.*, 1973, **82**, 629.
9. J. Brocas, *Theoret. Chim. Acta (Berl.)*, 1971, **21**, 79.
10. J. Brocas and R. Willem, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belges.*, 1973, **82**, 469.
11. J. Brocas, *Theoret. Chim. Acta*, 1985, **68**, 155.
12. N. Bej, D. C. Mukherjee and A. K. Mukherjee, *Mol. Phys.*, 2003, **101**, 865.
13. M. Randić, *J. Math. Chem.*, 1987, **1**, 145.
14. S. El-Basil, *Theoret. Chim. Acta*, 1984, **65**, 191.
15. S. El-Basil, *Theoret. Chim. Acta*, 1984, **65**, 199.
16. P. Ghosh and B. Mandal, *J. Math. Chem.*, 2010, **48**, 1069.
17. A. Chakrabarty and S. Mazumdar, *Phys. Rev. (B)*, 1999, **59**, 4839.
18. G. Heimel, P. Puschnig, M. Oehzelt, K. Hummer, B. Koppelhuber-Bitschnau, F. Porsch, C. Ambrosch-Draxl and R. Resel, *J. Phys. : Condens. Matter*, 2003, **15**, 3375.
19. A. Corney, J. Manners and C. E. Webb, *Opt. Commun.*, 1979, **31**, 354.
20. J. L. Nogue, S. Majewski, J. K. Walker, M. Bowen, R. Wojcik and W. V. Moreshead, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, 1988, **71**, 1159.
21. R. Tousey and I. Limansky, *Appl. Opt.*, 1972, **11**, 1025.

22. M. Era, T. Tsutsui and S. Saito, *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, 1996, **67**, 2436.
23. Y. Segawa, A. Fukazawa, S. Matsuura, H. Omachi, S. Yamaguchi, S. Irle and K. Itami, *Org. Biomol. Chem.*, 2012, **10**, 5979.
24. S. K. Maiti, *Physica (B)*, 2007, **394**, 33.
25. S. K. Maiti, *Chem. Phys.*, 2007, **331**, 254.
26. P. W. Fowler, B. T. Pickup and T. Z. Todorova, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 2008, **465**, 142.
27. P. W. Fowler, B. T. Pickup, T. Z. Todorova and T. Pisanski, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 2009, **130**, 174708.
28. S. Basu, P. Ghosh and B. Mandal, *Mol. Phys.*, 2008, **106**, 2507.
29. B. J. McClelland, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 2*, 1974, **70**, 1453.
30. B. J. McClelland, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 2*, 1982, **78**, 911.
31. B. J. McClelland, *Mol. Phys.*, 1982, **45**, 189.
32. J. R. Dias, *Intl. J. Quantum Chem.*, 1999, **74**, 721.
33. H. Hosoya, *J. Math. Chem.*, 1991, **7**, 289.
34. D. J. Klein, G. E. Hite, W. A. Seitz and T. G. Schmalz, *Theoret. Chim. Acta*, 1986, **69**, 409.
35. D. J. Klein and T. G. Schmalz, *Phys. Rev. (B)*, 1990, **41**, 2244.
36. A. Misra and D. J. Klein, *J. Chem. Inf. Comput. Sci.*, 2002, **42**, 1171.
37. H. Hosoya, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1971, **4**, 2332.
38. H. Narumi and H. Hosoya, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1980, **53**, 1228.
39. D. D. Keepports, *Theoret. Chim. Acta*, 1985, **67**, 491.
40. T. Lu, A. Tachinaba and T. Yamabe, *Int. J. Quantum Chem.*, 1990, **38**, 559.
41. I. Gutman, A. Nikolić and Ž. Tomović, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 2001, **349**, 95.
42. C. A. Coulson, *Proc. Cambridge Philos. Soc.*, 1940, **36**, 201.
43. I. Gutman, D. Vidović and B. Furtula, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 2002, **355**, 378.
44. L. Glass, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1975, **63**, 1325.
45. K. Kivelson and O. L. Chapman, *Phys. Rev.*, 1983, **28**, 7236.
46. S. S. D'Amato, B. M. Gimarc and N. Trinajstić, *Croat. Chem. Acta*, 1979, **54**, 1.
47. J. R. Dias, *J. Phys. Chem. (A)*, 1997, **101**, 7167.
48. R. Blankenbecler, D. J. Scalapino and R. L. Sugar, *Phys. Rev. (D)*, 1984, **24**, 2278.
49. S. E. Koonin, D. J. Dean and K. Langanke, *Phys. Rep.*, 1997, **278**, 1.